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Review Article

**REVIEW ON FLOATING DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM BY
USING NATURAL POLYMERS****K. Kavitha*, P.Sasikumari, A.Mavya Sri, M.Nagaambika, D.V.Saicharan and V.Saikishore**
Department of Pharmaceutics, Bapatla College of Pharmacy, Bapatla – 522101, India.**Abstract:**

The challenges of short gastric residence time and variable emptying rates, scientist have pursued advancements in rate-controlled oral drug delivery. This led to the development of gastro retentive systems, which prolongs drug retention in the stomach, improving absorption and efficacy. The development of rate-controlled oral drug delivery systems has gained significant attention in recent years, aiming to overcome physiological limitations such as unpredictable gastric emptying times and short gastric residence times. Specifically, floating drug delivery systems (FDDS) have emerged as a promising solution for drugs with narrow absorption windows, primarily absorbed in the stomach. By prolonging gastric retention, FDDS enhances bioavailability, reduces drug waste, and improves solubility for poorly soluble drugs. By preparing the floating drug delivery drugs natural polymers, such as Guar Gum, Xanthum Gum, Gum karya, Alginates chitosan Colocasia esculenta gum, fenugreek gum, locusta bean gum, mimosa mucilage okra gum, most frequently used polymers. IT plays a crucial role in FDDS formulation, offering biocompatibility, biodegradability, and cost- effectiveness .

Keywords: *Floating drug delivery system, Gastro-retentive drug delivery system, Natural of polymers of FDDS*

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INTRODUCTION:

Gastric dosage form that can be retained in the stomach for a prolonged period of time and release their active ingredients and thereby provide sustained and prolonged release of the drug to upper part of the gastrointestinal tract. (1)

Most of the versatile, convenient and widely utilized route of drug delivery for systemic action is oral route of administration. The development of oral drug delivery system for specific drug involves the drug optimization of the dosage form and characteristics of gastro intestinal physiology. (2) Among the oral route of administration, floating drug delivery provides more success to the researcher to develop the drugs the suitable environment is highly soluble at acidic environment and are unstable at alkaline environment. The floating drug delivery systems (FDSS) were first developed by Davis and described the literature in 1968. Davis developed a method to overcome problems like choking, gagging or expanded medicinal pills. He provided solution by providing

pills with a density is less than 1g/cm then pill easily floats on surface of water. (3) The source behind the FDSS is to making the dosage form to less dense than gastric fluids thereby easily with sufficient buoyancy to float over the gastric content and remain at surface of stomach without disturbing the gastric emptying rate for a prolonged period of time (4). Gastric retention is a way for the drug delivery in which shows desirable outcome the therapeutic benefit of drug. The retention time of drugs is narrow residence time in small intestinal region; longer residence time in stomach is an advantage for upper part of the small intestine. Thereby the drug is released slowly at desired rate, after release of drug the residual system is emptied from the stomach. The reason behind the increased residence time in stomach for better control fluctuations in plasma drug concentration. [5]

Floating drug delivery system offers a narrow absorption window by enabling prolonged gastric retention and enhanced bioavailability, thereby improved residence time.[6].

Figure 1: Strategies Of Gastroretentive Drug Delivery System.

Figure 2: Describes the classification of FDSS with physiochemical behavioral appearance

Need for gastroretention[7]

- Drugs that are absorbed from the proximal part of the gastrointestinal tract .
- Drugs that are less soluble or that degrade at the alkaline p^H .
- Drugs that are absorbed due to variable gastric emptying time.
- Local or sustained drug delivery to the stomach and proximal small intestine to treat certain conditions.
- Particularly useful for the treatment of gastric ulcers caused by H.Pylori infections.

Formulation considerations for GRDDS[7]

- It must be effective for retention in the stomach to suit the clinical demand.
- It must be convenient for intake to facilitate patient compliance.

- It must have sufficient drug loading capacity and control drug release profile.
- It must have full degradation and evacuation of the system once the drug release is over.
- It should not have effect on gastric motility including emptying pattern.
- It should not have other local adverse effects.

Drugs which can benefit from using gastroretentive devices[7]

- Drugs acting locally in the stomach.
- Drugs those are primarily absorbed in the stomach.
- Drugs those are poorly soluble at an alkaline p^H .
- Drugs with a narrow window of absorption.
- Drugs absorbed rapidly from the GI tract.
- Drugs those degrade in the colon.

Table 1:Relative parameters for conventional v/s gastro retentive drug deliveey system:

Relative parameters	Conventional drug delivery system	Gastro retentive drug delivery system	Reference
Toxicity	High risk of toxicity	Very low risk of toxicity	[8]
Patient compliance	Low	Improved	[8]
Drugs with poor solubility and high Ph	Not suitable for delivery of drugs with narrow absorption window in the small intestine region	Suitable for delivery of drugs with narrow absorption window in the small intestine region.	[9]
Drugs acting locally acting in the stomach.	Not much advantageous for drug having rapid absorption through GIT	Very much advantageous of drugs acting locally in the stomach	[9]
Dose dumping	No risk of dose dumping	Possibility of dose dumping	[8]

Mechanism of floating drug delivery system:

Floating drug delivery systems (FDDS) are designed to remain buoyant in the stomach for an extended period, releasing medication at a controlled rate. These low-density systems rely on buoyancy force (F) to stay afloat, necessitating minimal stomach content and floating force. The buoyancy retention principle is crucial for consistent gastro-retention. Researchers have developed a device to measure floating force kinetics, ensuring optimal FDDS performance. This apparatus continuously measures the force required to maintain buoyancy, optimizing stability and longevity.[10]

The floating force [F] is calculated as

$$F = F_{\text{buoyancy}} - F_{\text{gravity}} = (DF - DS) \cdot gv$$

Where:

DF=Fluid Density

DS = Object Density

V=volume

g= acceleration due to gravity

Figure 5: Types Of Dosage Forms In Floating Drug Delivery System

Natural polymers used in floating drug delivery system:

Plant-derived natural gums are high-molecular-weight hydrophilic polysaccharides. They exhibit poor solubility in organic solvents like hydrocarbons and ethers but demonstrate affinity for water. These gums can be categorized into two main types: water-soluble and water-absorbing. The former dissolves in cold water to form viscous solutions, while the latter swells and disperses in water, creating jelly-like textures. [11] The polymers are generally used in floating drug delivery system. So as to target the delivery drug to a

specific region in the gastrointestinal tract. I. e stomach. Polymers play a crucial role in enhancing drug solubility and targeting delivery. These macromolecular chains prevent precipitation, maintaining supersaturation and facilitating absorption. Moreover, these polymers are safer nontoxic and capable of chemical modification of and gel forming nature. [12]. They are so many advantages by using the natural polymers in FDDS as shown in figure 6:

Table 2: List of natural polymers used in floating drug delivery system and their sources

S. no	Natural polymer	Components of basic chain	Source	Reference
1	Alginates	1-4 linked, - β -D- mannuronic acid and α -L-glucuronic acid	Laminaria hyperborean, Ascophyllum, Nodosum , Macrocystis, Pyrifera etc.	13
2	Chitosan	Glucosamine and N-acetyl glucosamine	Shell of marine invertebrates	13
3	Colocasia esulenta gum	Oxalic acid Calcium phosphorus Niacin	Underground tubers of Colocasia esculenta.	13
4	Guar gum	[1-4] -6 -D-mannopyranosyl units with D-galacto pyranosyl units attached by (1-6) linkages	Seeds of Cyamopsis tetragonolobus kernels.	13
5	Gum karya	D-galactonic acid D-galactose, L-rhamnose.	Sterculiaurens Roxburgh and other species of sterculia.	13
6	Hibiscus mucilage	L-rhamnose-galactose-galacturonic acid D-glucuronic acid	Fresh leaves of hibiscus – rosa -sinesis	13
7	Locust bean gum	1,4 D-mannopyranosyl with C6 D-galacto pyranosyl unit	Endosperm seeds of carbo tree Ceratonia siliqua.	13
8	Mimosa mucilage	D-xylose and D-glucuronic acid	Seeds of Mimosa pudica	13
9	Okra gum	Galactose, galacturonic acid and rhamnose and some fraction of glucose, arabinose and xylose.	Fresh fruits of the plant Abelmoschus esculents	13
10	Carrageenan	Galactose and 3,6 anhydro galactose	Red seaweed species like Eucheuma gigartia stellate.	13
11	Pectin	D-galacturonic acid	Citrus peel, apple pomace, sugar beet pulp.	14
12	Gellan gum	D- glucose, D-glucuronic acid and rhamnose in β -1,4 linkage	Pseudomonas elodea	14
13	Psyllium husk starch	B-(1-4)-linkedD-Xylopyranosyl α – (1,4) linked D-glucose and α -(1,6)-linked D-glucose	Seed coats of Plantago avata storage polysaccharide in plants	14
14	Xanthum- gum	B-(1,4)- linked D-glucose	Fermentation of glucose by Xanthomonas campestris	14

Table 3: List of drugs by using natural polymers in floating drug delivery system:

S.no	Drug name	Activity	Natural polymers	Formulation	Method	Reference
1	Esomeprazole magnesium trihydrate	Anti-ulcer	Moringa gum, Azadirachta indica gum, xanthum gum	Floating Tablet	direct compression technology	15
2	Nicorandil	Treat angina	xanthum gum and guar gum	Floating Tablets	Direct compression.	16
3	Famotidine	Anti -ulcer	Rice bran wax	Floating Tablets	hot melt granulation technique	17
4	Nizatidine,	Treat stomach ulcers, ulcerative esophagitis	Mimosa gum	Effervescent gastric floating matrix tablets	rotary tablet punching machine	18
5	Levocetirizine	Anti -histaminic	Locust bean gum	Floating Tablets	direct compression method	19
6	Isradipine	Anti-hypertensive	karaya gum	Floating Tablets	direct compression method	20
7	Lovastatin	HMG (COA) reductase inhibitor	Guar gum	Floating Tablets	direct compression method	21
8	Captopril	anti- hypertensive agent treat congestive heart failure	karaya gum, badam gum	Floating Tablets	Direct Compression Method	22
9	Acyclovir	Anti-viral agents	Xanthan-Gum, Guar-gum	Floating Tablets	directly compressed	23
10	metformin hydrochloride	Anti - diabetic	okra gum and fenugreek gum.	Floating Tablets	Compression method	24
11	Hydralazine Hydrochloride	Treatment of hypertension and congestive heart failure	Cashew gum	Floating Tablets	direct compression method	25
12	Baclofen	skeletal muscle relaxant	Guar gum, xanthan gums	Floating Tablets	dry granulation technique	26
13	metformin HCl	non-insulin dependent diabetes mellitus (type II).	Tamarind kernel powder xanthan gum	Floating Tablets	using the wet granulation technique	27
14	famotidine	gastric ulcers, duodenal ulcers, Zollinger Elision syndrome and gastro esophageal reflux disease	Chitosan	Effervescent floating tablets	direct compression technique	28

15	Propranolol HCl	nonselective β -adrenergic blocker treat asthma, Anti-Hypertensive, Cardiovascular	Gaur gum, Pectin	Bilayer floating tablet	direct compression technology	29
16	Famotidine	Anti-ulcer activity inhibitor of histamine H ₂ receptors.	Xanthan gum and guar gum	FDSS tablets	wet granulation technique	30
17	Metformin Hydrochloride	Anti-diabetic	Gum Kondagogu	Effervescent granules	wet granulation method	31
18	Propranolol hydrochloride.	Antihypertensive, antianginal and antiarrhythmic	Xanthan gum,	Floating Tablets	directly compressed	32

APPLICATIONS [33]

1). Sustained drug delivery: Floating drug delivery systems release the drug over a prolonged period of time by retaining in the stomach for several hours and by increasing the gastric residence time.

2. Site specific drug delivery: Floating drug delivery systems are particularly useful for drugs having specific absorption from stomach or proximal part of the small intestine e.g. riboflavin, furosemide etc.

3. Absorption enhancement: Drugs that have poor bioavailability, because of their absorption is restricted to upper GIT are potential candidates to be formulated as floating drug delivery systems, thereby improving their absolute bioavailability.

4. Minimized adverse activity at the colon: Retention of the drug at the stomach (HBS system), minimizes the amount of drug that reaches the colon, that prevents the undesirable activities of the drug in colon.

5. Floating drug delivery systems are particularly useful for drugs which are poorly soluble or unstable in intestinal fluids and acid stable drugs and for those which undergo abrupt changes in their pH-dependent solubility due to pathophysiological conditions of GIT, food and age, e.g. floating system for furosemide lead to potential treatment of Parkinson's disease.

CONCLUSION: Prolonging gastric retention through Floating Drug Delivery Systems (FDSS) has emerged as a promising strategy to enhance bioavailability of drugs with narrow absorption windows in the gastrointestinal tract. By extending drug residence time, FDSS improves solubility, reduces drug waste, and minimizes plasma level fluctuations. Natural polymers, such as guar gum, chitosan, xanthan gum, and locusta bean gum, play a pivotal role in FDSS formulations, offering biodegradability, biocompatibility, and eco-friendliness. These polymers have shown superior

performance over synthetic counterparts, enabling sustained and targeted drug delivery. The exploitation of plant-derived gums as novel natural polymers holds immense potential for future gastro-retentive system development, combining biocompatibility, patient tolerance, and local availability. This review highlights the dynamic role of natural polymers in floating drug delivery systems [FDSS] exploring their attributes, current research and future development.

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